

Geosuber Tool - Monitorization of the vitality of cork oak stands

Introduction

One of the objectives of this project was the development of an online tool to identify the dead cork oak trees inside a stand. This tool would use satellite images to identify the dead trees annually, efficiently and accurately, at the property scale, producing cartography that can be used as support for the bureaucratic procedure necessary to fill when cork oak trees are going to be cut (the bureaucratic procedure exist because cork oaks are a national protected tree in Portugal). This tool is also projected to have a mobile application/app, allowing it to be easily used in the field. As a secondary objective this tool would allow the collection of vast amounts of data that can be analysed to better understand the decrease of vitality of cork oak stands at different geographical scales.

Besides detecting mortality, the project also tried to understand the relation between the change of leaves in the tree canopy and the ideal timing to start debarking, which is when the cork cambium/phellogen starts its activity. In theory the activity should start at the same time as the secondary growth of the tree, however it is very difficult to accepted this as a fact since no technic allows the measurement of the cork growth without also measuring the growth of wood. For the sake of this experiment and the discussion of the results it was hypothesised that the wood cambium/vascular cambium starts the activity at the same time as the cork cambium.

For the creation of the previously mentioned tool 1 field visit was done to install the continuously measured plots, 24 flights with drones using a multispectral image capturing device were done between 2018 and 2020, and 12 multispectral satellite images from Sentinel-2A and Pleides-1A were analysed. In the plots installed it was quantified, besides the measurements of the trees and the characterization of the plot, variables related to the tree phenological state, such as dead fallen leaves biomass and cork humidity. The data collected was analysed, corrected and different vegetation indexes were created. The data and indexes, plus climatic data, was fitted into different models, possible correlations were analysed and the adjustment of the models was done by verifying their predictions in the field.

The results show that the blossoming of new leaves is controlled by the sum of time in which the temperature is above a certain base value. It was proven that the secondary growth of the tree started with the blossoming of the new leaves. By this statement and what was told above we can hypothesise that the cork cambium also starts the activity at the same time. The availability of water is the factor that determines the duration of time in which secondary growth is active.

The model created to detect the vitality trees, analysed multispectral images creating vegetation indexes, allowing the detection of dead trees with an accuracy between 85% to 70% (best and worst result in the plots used), however it was demonstrated that the model needs to be fitted to each study area, so a “correction” plot needs to be installed wherever the model is used. From the two time periods that the data was collected (Spring and Autumn), the model differentiated between healthy and unhealthy trees with more accuracy in the period of September to October. The accuracy of the model is affected by the existence of saplings/small trees, because they are miscategorised. This model allowed the tool to differentiate between healthy trees, dead/sick trees, and suspicious trees (maybe dead/sick trees), producing a report and cartography that is delivered to the forest owner.

Lessons learned

Typically forest management is done by plots, with the same characteristics and applied operations. A new management approach, with a more adapted scale in relation to space and time is needed to face the new challenges that are coming with the climate change. By continuously monitoring the trees of a stand, using resources such as LIDAR, Drones and satellite images it is possible to know the vitality state of each individual in a stand, in this way creating a tool that allows the detection of less vigour trees, that can be cause for example by pest and diseases or water deficits, and even detecting the trees that are dead.

The tool created by this project is going to allow forest owners and forest workers to have an up to date knowledge about the state of vitality of their property, being able to quickly identify the location of dead trees. This tool has a huge potential in Portugal, since identifying the location of dead cork oak trees is necessary to fill the paper needed to cut dead cork oak trees.

In the future, it is of most importance that this tool continues to develop and leaves its prototype stage, for it to be able to be used in the “real world”.

Figure 1. Tree vitality state using tools such as LIDAR, Drones and satellite images

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Further information

<https://www.unac.pt/index.php/id-i/grupos-operacionais-accao-1-1-pdr2020/geosuber>

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